

Seminar on Human Rights and ICT Standardisation

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Brussels and Online

POST EVENT REPORT

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Executive summary

Purpose of the event

Information and Communications Technology (ICT) standardisation is undergoing a paradigm shift. Historically focused on issues like interoperability, security, speed, and technical efficiency, Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and national bodies are now actively integrating **human rights frameworks** directly into the technical fabric of digital technologies. It still, nevertheless, remains uneven across bodies and several of the practices that do circulate in policy discourse are either aspirational or partial rather than fully institutionalised.

Because standards act as “soft law” and dictate how software, algorithms, and networks operate globally, embedding human rights at the design phase ensures that protections for privacy, non-discrimination, and accessibility are built-in rather than bolted-on.

With this premise, on the 14th April 2026, the European Commission, in cooperation with the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR)¹ and supported by the EC funded projects StandICT.eu 2029, INSTAR and Indico Global, organised the [Seminar on Human Rights and ICT Standardisation](#) in Brussels, Belgium as a dedicated occasion to assess how human rights considerations can be embedded more concretely and systematically into ICT standards development. Bringing together over 190 registrants and 100 live participants in person or online representing standards bodies, policymakers, industry and SMEs, academia, civil society and the human rights community, the workshop highlighted practical examples already emerging across different organisations and regions.

Among these, the seminar drew upon valid initiatives showing different ways in which human rights can be operationalised in ICT standardisation. The examples discussed demonstrated that human rights are not an external add-on to standardisation, but are increasingly connected to ongoing technical work across multiple domains. This was demonstrated by some panelists through their work with the European network of national equalities bodies (Equinet), ANEC, and other civil society organisations on CEN-CENELEC JTC-21 standards specifically aimed at obtaining a presumption of conformity with the EU AI Act which requires AI systems ‘by design’ to afford a high-level of protection for health, safety and fundamental rights. This is also reflected in ITU-T, where human rights considerations are already relevant to areas such as sustainability and e-waste in Study Group 5, people-centred IoT and smart sustainable cities in Study Group 20, accessibility-related work in Study Group 21, and privacy and trust-related issues in Study Group 17. Other examples presented during the seminar further illustrated different levels of institutionalisation and operationalisation. The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has shifted toward systematically embedding democratic principles and fundamental rights into its structural processes. ETSI’s published standards-making process describes openness, transparency, impartiality, consensus, effectiveness, relevance, coherence and a care for the development dimension, IPR rules, public enquiry and weighted voting, but does not, as of now, include a formalised human rights impact assessment gate but it is introducing human rights assessments at defined stages of standards development. A similar move can be observed among some ITU Member States, where a proposal to establish a guideline on human-

¹ The UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, has produced two complementary reports, the first, **A/HRC/53/42 (2023)**, & the 2nd published in **Sept 2025** under the title “*Making technical standards work for humanity*”. Moreover, the **Global Digital Compact** (adopted at the UN General Assembly in 2024) directs the OHCHR to coordinate human rights considerations across global internet governance institutions, which gives the work an explicit UN-system mandate going forward.

centric approach to standardisation was made and is currently being deliberated by the organisation². The IEEE 7000 series on value-based design and human wellbeing treats ethical values (fairness, transparency, privacy, autonomy, human dignity) as first-class engineering requirements and defines processes for value elicitation, prioritisation, ethical risk assessment, and transparency management. W3C's mandatory horizontal reviews is the closest thing to a formalised, mandatory rights-checkpoint regime; the five review groups concern accessibility, privacy, security, internationalisation and technical architecture, the work of Standards Australia on embedding human rights checkpoints in AI standardisation, and the use of ISO/IEC 42001 in Peru as part of a broader effort to connect AI governance with safeguards on non-discrimination, accessibility and data protection. Besides that, there are ongoing initiatives on ethics and human rights in AI standards developed in ISO/IEC and CEN-CENELEC.

This seminar should be understood as a new step in a broader process, which main landmarks are the 2024 events: first, the webinar on *Human Rights and ICT Standardisation*, organised with the support of the European Commission and the StandICT.eu 2026 and HSbooster.eu projects; and second the side event on *How can ICT standards ensure that human rights are upheld in the era of new and emerging technologies?*, co-organised by the European Commission, ITU, OHCHR, Czech Republic and France, held on the margins of the World Telecommunication Standardisation Assembly (WTSA), in New Delhi. Both [2024 post-event reports](#) established the rationale for a sustained dialogue between the human rights and standardisation communities, stressing the importance of an inclusive approach to broaden participation, continued multistakeholder collaboration and cooperation, stronger international coordination, consumer-centric approaches, and the need to embed human rights considerations throughout the standardisation lifecycle, including the need of involvement of human rights experts in the standardization process. In this sense, the 2026 Brussels seminar built on these previous discussions by showing which recommendations identified in 2024 are beginning to translate into concrete practices and which, conversely, remain outstanding.

Figure 1 - First Panel “The Human Rights dimension of ICT standards”

² Contribution C36 on follow up to the human rights and standardization by Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, European Union (Belgium), Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Montenegro, Netherlands (Kingdom of the), Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine; available at <https://www.itu.int/md/T25-TSAG-C-0036/en>.

Where we stand: a comparison with the recommendations of our previous 2024 events

A first recommendation from 2024 events that can now be regarded as implemented is the **call for ongoing collaboration and continued dialogue**. The seminar held in Brussels itself constitutes one example of the continuation of the process initiated two years ago and confirms that this topic requires sustained engagement. Also, the OHCHR study on technical standards and human rights, published in 2025, shows concrete examples in which this engagement has been fruitful.³

Closely linked to this, the 2024 recommendation on **strengthened international cooperation** has also been materially advanced. The present report documents concrete examples of cross-organisational cooperation, including collaboration among ITU, ISO, IEC and OHCHR leading to the [Seoul Statement on AI standards](#), as well as broader evidence that rights-aware ICT standardisation increasingly depends on cooperation across disciplines, institutions and regions.

The 2024 recommendation to **highlight best practices** can likewise be considered implemented through the present report with several specific examples showing how different organisations are beginning to operationalise human rights in standards development, as presented in chapter 2.

The 2024 recommendation to **integrate human rights experts and organisations into standardisation activities** has also moved from principle to early implementation, at least in some contexts. CEN-CENELEC has active engagement in working groups from Liaisons representing human rights expertise. ETSI's possibility for technical committees to consult external human rights experts, IEEE's structured multidisciplinary model, and the Australian example of coordination among regulators, industry, technical experts and human rights institutions all show that more structured forms of interdisciplinary involvement are emerging.

Other 2024 recommendations should be considered **partially or not yet implemented**. This applies particularly to the ambition of linking technical concepts to human rights and moving towards **human rights by design**. The translation gap between human rights concepts and engineering language and the **lack of a common vocabulary** are still seen as some of the central unresolved problems, which means that operationalisation has started but is not yet sufficiently systematic or shared across SDOs. Where it has been successful, lessons need to be learned. But there is significant progress in ongoing initiatives on AI Ethics and social concerns in CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC, and W3C, including discussions on threat modelling using the LEGO® Serious Play® methodology and a human rights framework⁴. Regarding the need for stronger **training and capacity-building**, some examples such as the ISO capacity building workshops on the AI Policy and Standards, in which OHCHR brought a human rights approach is a good example that can serve as a reference to other SDOs⁵. The same reasoning applies in particular to recommendations about the reduction of barriers to participation, and for broader inclusion of civil society, including stakeholders with more limited resources and those from underrepresented regions. Also, it can be observed that some actors begun to operationalize the recommendation on building **processes and tools to conduct human rights due diligence**. ETSI, for instance, developed a structured and exploratory process using checkpoints and checklists to help technical committees identify and address potential human rights impacts throughout the lifecycle of a standard.

3 OHCHR. Making technical standards work for humanity: New pathways for incorporating international human rights into standards development for digital technologies. September 2025. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/issues/civicspace/resources/civic-space-study-tech-standard-setting.pdf>

4 See: [Threat Modelling with LEGO SERIOUS PLAY: Building your Digital Identity threat | 2025 | Blog | W3C](#).

5 See: OHCHR, Making standards work for humanity. And https://mcit.gov.eg/en/Media_Center/Latest_News/News/71545

This broader diagnosis, on the need for stronger capacity building and a clear process to embed human rights, is also reflected in internal work conducted within ITU-T. An internal survey across ITU-T study groups and TSAG showed broad recognition of the relevance of human rights to standardisation, with 84 per cent of respondents considering them relevant to ITU-T work. At the same time, 40 per cent reported low or no familiarity with human rights concepts, confirming that awareness is growing but remains uneven. The survey also found that human rights considerations are already present in areas such as privacy, accessibility, safety and non-discrimination, but that integration remains fragmented, mostly ad hoc, and not yet supported by an ITU-T-wide process. It is clear that in order to enable greater understanding of the impacts on human rights of new and emerging technologies that the training and capacity building should be two-way: human rights experts to technologist.

How to use this report

This report is intended to function as a practical bridge between communities that often work separately. It is primarily addressed to standards bodies, technical committees, working groups, study groups, regulators, industry actors and policymakers who need concrete examples of how human rights considerations can be embedded into standardisation processes. It is equally relevant for human rights experts, civil society organisations and academic actors who may be less familiar with how standards are developed, but whose expertise is increasingly necessary if human rights are to be translated into operational design requirements, review practices and governance mechanisms. At the same time, it is also potentially useful for readers who are new to either field, by providing both conceptual framing and practical examples that clarify why the intersection between human rights and ICT standardisation matters and how it can be acted upon.

This report is structured to support these different types of readers and uses: the section on *why a dialogue between human rights and ICT standardisation is needed* provides the overall rationale and context; the *best practices* section offers concrete examples of measures already emerging across SDOs and national contexts; the section on *guidelines, processes and supporting measures* is intended as a practical reference for those seeking to translate principles into working methods, while the *next calls to action* section identifies the main priorities for follow-up.

1. Why a dialogue between Human rights and ICT standardisation is needed now

Digitisation of society is a fact. Digital technologies are pervasive and more and more present in all aspects of modern life. Technical standards increasingly define the architecture of digital society itself. If human rights expertise is absent from these processes, societies risk embedding harmful assumptions directly into the technical foundations of future technologies. But if both communities work together early enough, standardisation can become a powerful mechanism for building digital systems that are not only interoperable and efficient, but also trustworthy, inclusive and aligned with human rights and democratic values.

Technical standards are not neutral. They can shape how digital technologies affect people's rights, including privacy, dignity, equality, accessibility, freedom of expression and non-discrimination⁶. For this reason, embedding human rights into ICT standards is not only a matter of legal compliance, but also a condition for trust, accountability and inclusiveness in the digital economy.

At the same time, both communities are increasingly confronting different but interconnected forms of systemic instability. Within the standards community, concerns are growing around fragmentation, legitimacy, geopolitical divergence, trust, implementation chaos and sovereignty tensions. Human rights communities, meanwhile, are increasingly focused on concentration of power, opacity, exclusion, surveillance and the emergence of unaccountable digital infrastructures. These concerns are often discussed separately, yet they increasingly stem from the same technological transformations.

Digital technologies are no longer neutral infrastructures operating in the background of society, they formulate the backbone of societal operation, engagement and inclusions. AI systems, connected devices, biometric technologies and future 6G networks increasingly shape how people access information, work, engage democratically and participate in society. As these technologies become embedded into everyday life, technical standards increasingly influence human rights. Technical design choices are therefore no longer purely engineering matters. They directly affect non-technical issues like privacy, freedom of expression, accessibility, non-discrimination and democratic participation.

Human rights cannot be treated as a downstream compliance exercise. Biases, exclusion mechanisms and surveillance-oriented design choices can become embedded directly into infrastructures and standards. Once technical architectures, data models and system requirements are defined, many risks become difficult, expensive or even impossible to correct. Standards must therefore become "human-centred by design", embedding human rights considerations from the earliest phases of technical development rather than reviewing them only after deployment.

This requires a structural dialogue between the human rights and standards development communities. Human rights principles are often expressed in legal terms, following the international human rights law, while standards developers work with highly technical specifications, protocols and engineering requirements. Without a shared framework or common vocabulary and mutual interpretation of what and how protections are upheld, it becomes difficult to translate concepts such as fairness, dignity, transparency or non-discrimination into concrete technical requirements that can actually be implemented, tested and measured within standards. This translation gap and difficulty translating human rights principles into technical requirements is one of the main challenges in linking human rights and ICT standardisation.

The first requirement for the success of standards that respect human rights is to align them with companies' practices and decision-making process, in order to make them actionable. The culture and mechanics of

⁶ On the human rights impacts of technical standards, see: OHCHR, A/HRC/53/42, para. 17-25.

organisational policies and operations are usually based on corporate code of ethics (general or particular fields, e.g. digital, AI...)

Nowadays there is an intense activity, even at institutional and political level, on ethics and social concerns in ICT (AI, neuro-IT, robotics...). The primary challenge for ICT standardisation respecting human rights is to manage the intertwined nature of human rights and ethical aspects, translating them into standards in a practically viable manner. This requires connecting them with corporate mechanisms for the development and oversight of the code of ethics, as well as with its expression in corporate policies and throughout the life cycle of ICT products and services.

Bridging this gap is not a simple exercise. It requires conscious implementation of capacity building and awareness-raising activities aimed at achieving a common understanding. It is increasingly necessary for preserving the stability, interoperability and legitimacy of global digital ecosystems. Rights-aware standardisation should therefore not be understood as anti-innovation or as an external constraint imposed on technical development. Rather, it can function as a stabilising governance mechanism capable of supporting globally interoperable systems while reducing social, political and regulatory friction.

Standardisation offers something human rights frameworks often struggle to provide on their own: operationalisation. Standards can transform abstract principles into measurable requirements, repeatable processes and practical organisational checkpoints. Therefore, human rights experts cannot remain external observers of technical standardisation processes. Their role must evolve to actively contribute to standardisation efforts.

Standardisation initiatives on human rights should be connected with corporate mechanisms for the development and oversight of the code of ethics, as well as with their expression in corporate policies and throughout the life cycle of ICT products and services.

In this regard, it is particularly important to highlight the role of all organisational positions involved in the life cycle of ICT products and services. Human rights concerns related to ICT are multidisciplinary in nature; however, for success in translating respect for human rights dimension into ICT practice, it is essential that Member States and Standards Development Organisations strengthen the institutional frameworks, capacity-building initiatives, training programmes, multi-stakeholder engagement mechanisms, and participatory governance structures needed to embed professional excellence, ethical responsibility, and human rights considerations throughout the digital ecosystem. Human rights compliance cannot be merely a matter of compliance oversight. Instead, it must become part of everyday attitudes and processes throughout the life cycle of ICT products and services, and especially part of the work of the professionals who conceive, implement, and operate them within organisations.

Recent developments within ITU also show that this dialogue is gradually moving closer to the mainstream of ICT standardisation. WTSA-24 marked an important step in this direction: the side event on ICT standards and human rights brought together ITU, OHCHR, governments and industry representatives⁷, while the Freedom Online Coalition (FOC) statements highlighted the connection between technical standards, AI standards, human rights and the Sustainable Development Goals.⁸ Discussions around AI and metaverse-related standardisation further confirmed that human rights considerations are becoming visible in ITU and Council of Europe debates⁹.

7 See: [WTSA Side Event: How can ICT standards ensure that human rights are upheld in the era of new and emerging technologies?](#)

8 See: [Joint Statement on Technical Standards and Human Rights in the Context of Digital Technologies - Freedom Online Coalition. Joint Statement on Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights \(2025\) - Freedom Online Coalition](#)

9 See: Council of Europe and IEEE. "The Metaverse and its Impact on Human Rights, Rule of Law, and Democracy". Available at: <https://rm.coe.int/the-metaverse-and-its-impact-on-human-rights-the-rule-of-law-and-democ/1680b178b0>

Additionally, global technologies are developed for highly diverse societies with different legal systems, cultural expectations and developmental priorities. Human rights-based ICT standardisation therefore cannot rely on a single regional perspective. Inclusiveness, multistakeholder participation and stronger representation from underrepresented regions are therefore essential conditions not only for building standards that reflect the needs and rights of diverse populations, but also for reducing geopolitical fragmentation and strengthening the global legitimacy and adoption of technical standards. Whilst states are primarily responsible for promotion and protection of human rights, it must be noted that private actors must also recognise their responsibilities, under the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, in the designing and deployment of digital technologies. This approach is further underpinned by the universality of human rights, which, in order to be meaningfully realised, require standardisation processes to take into account the full diversity of human experiences and contexts.

The question is no longer whether human rights are relevant to ICT standards, but how to integrate them more systematically, practically and consistently across the standardisation process. This is also paramount to ensure wide implementation of the ICT standards.

Figure 2 - Second Panel “How to ensure that ICT standards uphold Human Rights”

2 Best practices

Several Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) are already integrating human rights considerations into ICT standardisation through practical and scalable approaches across technical work, governance, and stakeholder engagement. This paragraph summarises the main examples shared during the event across various SDOs, topics and geographies.

Examples from SDOs

ETSI

In 2025, ETSI launched an initiative on “Standardisation and Human Rights” introducing human rights assessments directly into standards development workflows. ETSI developed a structured process to help technical committees identify and address potential human rights impacts throughout the lifecycle of a standard. This exploratory process will now enter into a test phase collecting information about the practical use of it. The initiative established three formal checkpoints: at the creation of a new work item, during the first stable draft, and before final adoption.

At each stage, committees are encouraged to assess whether a proposed standard could affect human rights and whether additional mitigation measures or external expertise were required. The exploratory framework drew on key international references, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the European Convention on Human Rights, the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, and the Freedom Online Coalition principles. Where technical committees lack the expertise to properly assess these impacts, ETSI will enable consultation with external human rights specialists, including potential support from organisations such as the EU Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA). The process is about to be introduced as an exploratory mechanism and tested with selected committees before possible wider adoption across ETSI standardisation activities. ETSI highlighted several illustrative risk areas, including privacy concerns linked to location tracking, metadata collection, encryption and anonymity choices, accessibility barriers affecting persons with disabilities or multilingual communities, and algorithmic bias and discrimination in AI systems such as facial recognition and recruitment technologies.

IEEE

IEEE presented Ethically Aligned Design **Ethically Aligned Design (EAD)** as one of the earliest structured initiatives to integrate ethics and human rights into the design of emerging technologies, especially AI and intelligent autonomous systems. The initiative started in 2016, when IEEE recognized that technological innovation could no longer be addressed only from a technical perspective, but also required consideration of its societal and human rights impacts. A key aspect of the initiative was its multidisciplinary approach. IEEE expanded the discussion beyond engineers and involved philosophers, medical experts, policy specialists and human rights stakeholders to better understand both the risks and opportunities created by emerging technologies. This collaborative process lasted three years and resulted in the publication of the [Ethically Aligned Design report](#), an open and publicly available document intended to guide responsible technology development. According to IEEE, one of the most important outcomes of the initiative was the recognition of human rights as a foundational design principle for technology systems. These principles were later adopted across IEEE as

guiding references for future standardization activities. The initiative also led to the development of the IEEE P7000 series, a family of standards designed to operationalize ethical and human rights principles into technical requirements and engineering practices. IEEE 7000 introduced a value-based and risk-based methodology to identify relevant human values in a specific context and integrate them directly into system design. Other standards from the series focus in more detail on specific human rights related aspects as privacy or bias. In addition, an ethical [certification program](#) has been developed. IEEE CertifAIEd helps individuals and organizations demonstrate responsible AI implementation, rooted in a comprehensive ethical framework encompassing transparency, accountability, bias, and privacy.

The standards and certifications have already been tested in practical implementations, including projects in Austria and Korea. IEEE highlighted a recent standard that defines requirements and processes for the responsible and ethical procurement of AI systems. [IEEE 3119](#) focuses on building ethical considerations into different stages of the procurement process. Another important outcome was the work on children's rights in digital environments, developed in collaboration with the Five Rights Foundation. This work contributed to standards on age verification and age-appropriate design, addressing concerns related to manipulation, mental health and the protection of minors online. The [IEEE 2089-2021 Standard](#) provides guidelines for tech companies to build digital services with children's rights, developmental needs, and safety in mind. Effective human rights standardization requires cooperation beyond the standardization community itself. For this reason, the initiative involved collaborations with organizations such as UNICEF, the Council of Europe, the OECD and the Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights.

ITU

ITU-T presented ongoing efforts to move from awareness-raising towards more practical implementation of human rights considerations in technical standardisation. Over the past 2 years, this work has included internal awareness-raising, an analytical report presenting the results of an internal survey on human rights integration across ITU-T study groups and TSAG, and a comparative study of human rights practices across standards development organisations and related bodies¹⁰. These activities confirmed both growing recognition of the relevance of human rights to ICT standards and the need for practical support to help engineers translate broad human rights principles into technical requirements.

A central message from ITU-T was that human rights should not be treated as external legal or policy concerns that are added after technical work has been completed. Instead, they need to be considered directly within technical design processes. Simply inserting human rights language into standards is not sufficient. Effective integration requires practical methodologies, examples and review mechanisms that can help technical experts identify possible impacts on rights such as privacy, accessibility, safety, non-discrimination and freedom of expression.

ITU-T also underlined that this work requires a better understanding of the trade-offs that may arise between different technical and societal objectives, as well as of the less visible impacts that may result from opaque profiling, inference-based systems or persuasive design choices that shape what users see, believe or choose without their meaningful awareness. Objectives such as privacy, security, safety, resilience, child protection and non-discrimination may sometimes require different or even competing technical choices. In addition, systems that classify users, draw inferences about them or influence their behaviour may raise concerns related to privacy, autonomy, freedom of thought and opinion, non-discrimination, transparency, contestability and user control. These issues therefore need to be addressed through context-specific technical assessment rather than through abstract principles.

¹⁰ See: [TSAG-TD259](#) and [TSAG-TD260](#).

ITU-T analytical report brings many examples from ITU-T's work showing that human rights considerations are already relevant across several areas of standardisation, including privacy and trust, accessibility, sustainability, smart sustainable cities and emerging technologies such as AI. One lesson from this experience is that early engagement matters: potential human rights concerns are easier to identify and address while a standard is still being drafted than after technical choices have already been fixed.

Looking ahead, ITU-T highlighted the importance of developing more systematic approaches to support rights-aware standardisation. This could include targeted training, practical guidelines, examples from other SDOs, and tools to assist technical committees in identifying and addressing human rights implications throughout the standards development lifecycle. The overall objective is to move from general recognition of the relevance of human rights towards more consistent, practical and operational integration across ICT standardisation development processes.

W3C

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) presented a best practice focused on integrating human rights considerations early in the standards development. Rather than relying only on late-stage review, the objective is to embed these considerations directly into the design phase of technical standards. This approach emerged from the recognition that late-stage reviews often create delays, tensions and incomplete solutions, while many risks could be identified earlier through structured design processes. A central element of this approach is the use of horizontal review groups dedicated to areas such as accessibility, privacy, security and internationalization.

Rather than concentrating relevant expertise in a single body, W3C distributes these competencies across multiple review structures to ensure that different perspectives are considered throughout the development process. However, this also created practical challenges, since technical groups need to engage with several review communities, each with its own terminology, timing and expectations. To address these challenges, W3C uses and is developing practical tools and facilitation methods aimed at helping engineers better understand human rights implications. These included questionnaires, common vocabularies, facilitation exercises and methodologies inspired by threat modelling practices already used in cybersecurity. The purpose was to make abstract rights-related concepts such as privacy and accessibility more concrete and understandable for technical experts. One example, in some workshop settings, was the use of collaborative exercises and metaphors to demonstrate how different people may interpret the same concept differently. This approach was used to show that concepts linked to human rights, such as privacy or accessibility, can vary significantly depending on cultural, social and contextual perspectives. These facilitation methods helped participants move beyond purely technical reasoning and better understand the real-world impact of design choices. Another important practice involved increasing collaboration between engineers, lawyers, policymakers and civil society organizations directly within the standards development process. The objective was not only to include external feedback, but to create continuous interaction between technical and non-technical stakeholders during drafting activities. To support this process, W3C also started initiatives aimed at helping policymakers understand how to interact more effectively with engineers and technical communities. The W3C experience demonstrated that early integration, transparency about assumptions and continuous multidisciplinary collaboration can help produce more trustworthy and socially responsible standards while reducing risks that may otherwise emerge after deployment.

IDPF and W3C

In some areas, a significant amount of work has already been done, and established best practices can now be shared across industries. One of the clearest examples comes from digital publishing, where accessibility has become a key driver of innovation in technical standards and editorial workflows over the past few years. This transformation has been strongly influenced by international regulations such as the European Accessibility Act (EAA) and the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA), which recognise access to digital content as a fundamental right and require e-books and digital publications to be accessible to all readers, including persons with disabilities. Before these developments, the digital publishing ecosystem had already reached a relatively mature stage with EPUB 3, an open digital publishing standard originally developed by the International Digital Publishing Forum (IDPF) and now maintained within the W3C, with broad adoption across the publishing industry. At that stage, the standard was often regarded as sufficiently advanced for mainstream publishing needs. However, accessibility requirements revealed important structural limitations in how digital publications were designed, produced, and distributed. This led publishers, technology providers, and standards organizations to rethink the entire publishing workflow through a more inclusive and rights-based perspective. As a result, a large part of the recent evolution of the EPUB standard has been driven by accessibility-related needs. Accessibility is no longer treated as an optional feature added at the end of the production process, but increasingly as a core requirement embedded from the beginning. This shift has contributed to improving equal access to information, culture, and education for persons with visual, cognitive, and motor impairments, while also promoting better semantic structures, stronger interoperability between platforms, and more inclusive digital ecosystems overall.

NEN

A best practice emerged from the Dutch national standardisation experience, facilitated by NEN, where work was carried out within the national standardisation system to address bias and discrimination risks in algorithmic systems used by public authorities. The initiative focused on the development of a Dutch Technical Agreement (NTA), a consensus-based standardisation document developed through a fast-track process, dedicated to profiling algorithms adopted by government institutions. Instead of approaching human rights only at a high-level policy dimension, the work concentrated on a very specific and operational use case in order to make discussions more concrete and actionable. The process involved a multidisciplinary working group bringing together civil society representatives, statisticians, lawyers, philosophers and technical experts. Since many participants were not familiar with standardisation processes, extra time was given to informing people of the principles of standardization work. Informal “buddy” mechanisms were also used to help participants understand technical discussions and collaborate more effectively across disciplines. A key lesson learned from this experience was that integrating human rights into ICT standardisation becomes more effective when discussions focus on concrete and contextualized problems rather than only abstract principles. Working on a narrowly defined case helped participants identify practical areas where consensus could be achieved and enabled technical, legal and societal perspectives to interact more productively. The experience demonstrates the value of consensus-building between stakeholders with different professional backgrounds and perspectives. The initiative also exposed important limitations and governance challenges. In particular, discussions frequently raised questions about the boundary between technical standardisation and legal interpretation, especially regarding whether algorithmic discrimination could be fully addressed through technical methods alone. This highlighted the meaning of technical standards to support, but not replace, legal interpretation and judicial assessment. As a result, the work evolved toward developing technical guidance and documentation

that can help present statistical evidence and algorithmic assessments in a manner that is more transparent and accessible to judges, regulators and legal experts.

ISO/IEC

Another relevant best practice emerged from the Peruvian standardisation and regulatory experience, where efforts have focused on creating stronger operational links between AI regulation, technical standards and implementation practices. The discussion highlighted that Peru recently introduced AI regulation containing safeguards related to human rights, including non-discrimination and accessibility requirements. At the same time, the national standardisation body formally adopted ISO/IEC 42001 on AI management systems as a Peruvian technical standard to provide organizations with a structured framework for managing AI risks, bias, transparency and data protection. The experience showed that the existence of principles and regulations alone is not sufficient to ensure effective human rights protection in practice. Many companies still develop AI products and services primarily in response to market demand and competitive pressure, without systematically integrating human rights requirements during the design phase. This created the need for stronger operational mechanisms capable of translating high-level principles into measurable compliance activities and technical controls. A key aspect of the best practice was therefore the effort to connect three different layers of the ecosystem: technical committees responsible for drafting standards, regulators responsible for human rights obligations, and companies responsible for implementing technical and organisational controls. The objective was to create a clearer relationship between principles, technical requirements and evidence-based compliance processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the need to complement international standards with implementation tools capable of supporting practical adoption. These included sector-specific guidance, implementation examples, assessment criteria and clearly defined competencies for auditors and evaluators. The experience demonstrated that human rights integration becomes more effective when organizations are supported not only by principles and standards, but also by concrete operational guidance that helps transform ethical and legal requirements into verifiable technical practices. Additional initiatives such as ISO/IEC 22443 Artificial Intelligence Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations, are expanding ISO/IEC 42001 dimension on responsible use of AI.

CEN/CENELEC and Liaison Status

The European Committee for Standardization is putting in value existing standards on digital ethics such as CEN/TS 17834:2022: European Professional Ethics Framework for the ICT Profession (EU ICT Ethics), as starting point for incorporating human rights and for managing, in a practical way, the intertwined nature of human rights and ethical aspects in AI initiatives, translating them into standards in a practically viable manner. Both standardisation initiatives on human rights impact assessment and tools for integrating ethics into AI systems lifecycle, e.g. under development JT021034 - prCEN/TS Guidelines on tools for ethical aspects handling in AI systems life cycle. For example, the experience of JTC-21 EU AI Act standards by human rights expertise through EQUINET (whilst it has had its barriers) has demonstrated how lawyers can actively participate in working groups to translate important human rights such as Equality and Non-Discrimination into technical and procedural requirements helping providers of AI to design AI with fundamental rights risk management at their core. With the forthcoming prEN 18228 on risk management system to enable compliance with the EU AI Act provisions on risk (Article 9), this standard demonstrates the potential to be the first of its kind to facilitate technologists in designing AI systems with greater depth of understanding in how to protect against harms and hazardous situations brought about by the way technology is or is not designed.¹¹

¹¹ For further details see: <https://equineteurope.org/encoding-equality-in-ai-design-deliberation-and-oversight/> <https://ohrh.law.ox.ac.uk/how-can-we-guard-against-ai-generated-discrimination/> and Securing meaningful

Standards Australia

The Australian experience is a significant best practice, with specific examples of human rights expertise being systematically integrated into AI standardisation activities through direct participation in national technical committees. The approach was described as a practical example of how human rights considerations can be embedded into standardisation processes from the beginning rather than treated as external reviews conducted after technical work is completed. The experience was developed within Australia's national standardisation framework through participation in IT-043, the Standards Australia technical committee responsible for artificial intelligence. A distinctive element of this model is the direct involvement of the Australian Human Rights Commission within the committee itself. This created a structured mechanism allowing human rights expertise to work alongside engineers, data scientists, policymakers and industry stakeholders during standards development activities. The initiative demonstrated that standards are not purely technical instruments, but also normative tools capable of shaping how technologies are designed, deployed and governed before legislation or courts intervene. For this reason, the Australian approach focused on embedding human rights considerations directly into discussions related to fairness, transparency, accountability, safety and non-discrimination in AI systems. An important lesson learned from this experience was that technical excellence alone is not sufficient for trustworthy AI governance. The process showed the importance of creating multidisciplinary environments where technical experts and human rights specialists can work together continuously and not only through ad hoc consultations. This helped ensure that human rights concerns were considered as part of system quality and safety rather than external compliance obligations. The work also highlighted the value of translating abstract human rights principles into operational mechanisms already familiar within technical governance processes. Examples included impact assessments, stakeholder engagement procedures, transparency requirements, accessibility obligations and review mechanisms. According to the experience shared, these tools helped bridge the gap between high-level human rights principles and practical implementation within AI system design and governance. Another key outcome was the recognition that institutionalizing cooperation between standards bodies and human rights institutions can strengthen the long-term sustainability and credibility of ICT standardization processes. The Australian experience showed that embedding human rights expertise directly within technical committees can improve trust, support more inclusive innovation and help create standards that are more durable, socially responsible and better aligned with public expectations.

Figure 3 - Third Panel “What are standards organisations doing for human rights?”

3 Guidelines, processes and supporting measures

Based on the outcomes of the event, human rights integration in ICT standardisation should be built into the standards development process from the start, through a proportional process with clearer roles, better timing, more accessible participation formats, and stronger support for interdisciplinary exchange.

Guidance for standards bodies and standardisation experts

First, each new work item should include an early reflection on possible relevance for human rights. This should not require a full legal assessment in every case, but at least a short screening of whether the proposed standard may affect rights such as privacy, accessibility, non-discrimination, safety, participation, freedom of expression, or the rights of children and other vulnerable groups. Also, a pre-standardization phase can be useful to enable participation from diverse actors and to allow human rights concerns to be raised in advance of the standardization phase.

Secondly, human rights considerations should be reviewed again at defined stages of drafting. A practical minimum would be to introduce checkpoints at the beginning of the work, at first stable draft stage, and before final approval. At each stage, the committee should verify whether key concerns have been identified, whether relevant expertise has been consulted, and whether any major risks or trade-offs remain unaddressed.

Thirdly, meaningful participation is necessary to ensure that standards reflect not only technical requirements but also the needs, rights and experiences of the people and communities affected by the technologies they enable. This includes the participation of civil society organisations, human rights experts, consumer representatives, accessibility advocates, academia, and stakeholders from underrepresented regions and groups, whose perspectives may otherwise be overlooked. Committees should avoid assuming that formal openness is sufficient for meaningful participation. Being invited is not the same as being present, actively contributing, being heard, being understood and taken seriously. And all these are necessary to produce concrete results. If participation is to be substantive, supporting measures and proactive efforts to broaden engagement are needed. These may include funding mechanisms, developing innovative and low-barrier channels for inputs, fellowships, hybrid meetings, simplified background notes, short explanatory summaries for non-technical participants, non-technical participants, mentoring, coaching, and active facilitation to ensure that relevant stakeholders can contribute at the right stage of the process. Particular attention should also be given to creating incentives for sustained participation from academia. Standardisation Development Organisations (SDOs) should consider identifying authors in standards where appropriate, enabling such contributions to be recognised as scholarly outputs for academic career progression.

Fourthly, standardisation technical bodies (technical committees and working groups) should consider designating a focal point or rapporteur responsible for checking that human rights responsiveness is addressed throughout the work item. This function would not replace technical leadership, but would help ensure continuity, documentation and follow-up.

Finally, standards actors should recognise that not all standards need to follow a rigid one-size-fits-all logic. Requirements can be written as conditional statements. Where appropriate, standards may define core interoperable requirements but allow flexibility in implementation, interfaces or contextual adaptation. This is especially important where technologies affect diverse user groups, legal environments or social contexts.

” Guidance for human rights experts, civil society organisations and social stakeholders

Human rights actors should engage with standardisation as a site where rights are operationalised.

First, participation should begin as early as possible. Human rights concerns are more difficult to integrate once technical choices, data models or system architectures are already fixed. Early-stage engagement is therefore more effective than attempting to intervene only at final review.

Secondly, contributions should be framed in a way that can connect with technical work. Broad principles such as dignity, fairness, transparency, accessibility or non-discrimination are essential, but they need to be translated into more concrete questions. For example, which user groups may be excluded, which forms of harm are foreseeable, what kind of data practices may create risks, what degree of transparency is technically feasible, and how trade-offs between different rights should be addressed.

Thirdly, human rights actors should be prepared to work within iterative and consensus-based processes. Standardisation rarely progresses through single decisive interventions. Influence often depends on sustained participation, well-timed input, and the ability to engage with drafts, terminology and technical constraints over time.

Fourthly, civil society and rights experts should contribute evidence from lived experience, user needs and social impact.

Finally, human rights actors should also support the development of common vocabularies and practical reference tools. The workshop repeatedly highlighted that the lack of shared language between the two communities remains a major barrier. Human rights experts can help address this by contributing glossaries, examples, guidance notes, dedicated training and awareness-raising and case-based explanations that make rights concepts more usable in technical settings.

” Guidance for policymakers, regulators, governments, funders, academia, industry and other supporting actors

Other stakeholders have an important enabling role in making this dialogue sustainable and effective.

Policymakers and regulators should support frameworks that encourage the integration of human rights into standards processes without creating unnecessary delay or procedural overload. Their role should include supporting inclusive participation, encouraging evidence-based practices, and recognising that human rights integration can strengthen trust, regulatory alignment and overall quality of the implementation.

Academic actors should contribute more strongly to pre-normative work related to human rights. The discussions underlined that academia can play a major role in bridging conceptual gaps, testing methodologies, and producing the background work needed before formal standardisation starts. Greater recognition of standardisation-related work in academic careers of human rights experts would also help attract more sustained academic engagement.

Industry actors should not treat human rights only as an external compliance matter. Companies participating in standardisation should contribute practical experience on implementation challenges, interoperability needs, usability constraints and risk management, while also recognising the cost of not integrating rights considerations early enough.

Research and innovation projects can support experimentation with new participatory formats, pilot methodologies and assessment tools addressing human rights, including AI-based technologies and how

these can proxy human rights experts in their absence. They are also well placed to document case studies and share lessons related to human rights that may later feed into more formal standards work.

Funders have the responsibility to prioritize funding mechanisms that support meaningful participation in standardization processes through a human rights lens, sustain long-term projects, and focus on the Global South. A special support for human rights organizations and civil society is needed to identify key entry points within standardization organizations and to develop sustainable human rights agendas in these processes.

All the stakeholders should effectively engage in standard developing processes, whenever possible, in order to enrich those discussions with their perspectives and experience.

Figure 4 - Fourth Panel "The Way Forward"

4. Next calls to action

This section outlines concrete recommendations to strengthen cooperation between the human rights and ICT standardisation communities and support the practical integration of human rights considerations throughout standards development processes.

Call to actions and next steps from the event

↓ Promote structured dialogue and follow-up

As a first step, the report should be shared and discussed within international and national SDOs, as well as among human rights organisations, to create opportunities for feedback, alignment and cross-organisational exchange. These discussions can help identify common priorities, implementation gaps and areas for future cooperation involving SDOs, regulators, industry and civil society. A follow-up workshop within the next year could further assess progress made across participating organisations, while also providing space to share lessons learned, identify emerging challenges and showcase practical implementation experiences.

↓ Develop a common baseline methodology

At the operational level, a stronger focus should now be placed on developing a common baseline methodology to embed human rights expertise throughout the entire lifecycle of standards, from the creation of work items to final adoption and review. While each SDO currently follows its own approach, a shared methodology would provide a consistent starting point from which additional best practices, tools and implementation models could be developed and exchanged across organisations.

↓ Build a shared vocabulary

Supporting this effort also requires the creation of a shared vocabulary between technical and human rights communities. Actionable steps could include developing shared glossaries that connect human rights principles with technical definitions and measurable criteria, creating repositories of successful methodologies and implementation examples, and establishing reusable methodologies to assess how human rights considerations are integrated into standards development processes across SDOs. Joint workshops, multidisciplinary review groups and cross-sector pilot projects could further support more consistent interpretations of key concepts and strengthen their practical application within standards development activities.

↓ Strengthen inclusive and accessible stakeholder participation

Finally, broader cross-regional participation of civil society organisations and experts representing the field of human rights and other relevant disciplines remains essential to ensure that future standards are not only technically robust, but also trustworthy, inclusive and relevant. Achieving this will require more accessible participation mechanisms, including financial support programs, remote participation and AI-based proxy options, multilingual resources and targeted outreach initiatives. It will also require structured opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration throughout standards development processes.

Additional Call to actions and next steps

↓ StandICT.eu TWG

To follow up on the calls to action outlined in Section 4, a StandICT.eu Technical Working Group (TWG) on Human Rights will be established to support targeted efforts once priority areas are identified.

Leveraging the work started in 2024 and continued during the recent event in Brussels, the TWG will aim to continue to strengthen existing international collaboration and continue to source and highlight ongoing examples of best practice where organisations are beginning to operationalise human rights in standards development to support the integration of human rights considerations into ICT standardisation processes.

The TWG will further the ambition of linking technical concepts to human rights and moving towards human rights by design. To progress this, the TWG would aim to contribute to developing a shared vocabulary between technical and human rights communities, including common glossaries that link human rights principles with technical definitions and measurable criteria.

The TWG would also work to develop the basis for a common baseline methodology to embed human rights expertise throughout the entire lifecycle of standards including but not limited to identified recommendations such as: early reflection on possible relevance for human rights; a process for ensuring human rights considerations are reviewed at defined stages of drafting: ensuring that participation is meaningful and substantive; and that allow flexibility in implementation, interfaces or contextual adaptation of standards especially where technologies affect diverse user groups, legal environments or social contexts. In addition, the TWG would also examine routes to ensure broader participation from underrepresented regions, civil society organisations and interdisciplinary experts in this context.

↓ Webinars for awareness raising and promotion of this report

One of the training modules prepared under INSTAR to be delivered until the end of June will focus on human rights. Under the [StandICT.eu Academy](#) and co-organised with [EDU4Standards](#), a further webinar will be organised after the summer 2026 to discuss the role of human rights in standardisation. Eventually, this will lead to a further developed training module for the StandICT.eu Academy. The focus could be widened beyond the ICT area within the [HSBooster.eu II](#) project targeting standardisation in research projects in general. The projects will elaborate training modules for awareness raising, which can be made available to SDOs and human rights experts.

Future follow-up should also explore targeted capacity-building for standards participants, including training modules for standardisation technical experts through existing learning platforms offered by the standardisation Development Organizations (SDO). Such training could focus on how to identify human rights relevance in technical work items, how to translate human rights principles into engineering requirements, and how to use practical review tools, including AI-supported tools, to assist committees in early-stage assessment. Similarly, training programs on standardisation processes should be developed for Human Rights experts.

Appendix - Useful resources & sources for citation

- ▣ [Webinar recording](#)
- ▣ [Webinar slides](#)
- ▣ [WTSA Side Event: How can ICT standards ensure that human rights are upheld in the era of new and emerging technologies?](#)
- ▣ [StandICT.eu Academy](#)
- ▣ [INSTAR Human Rights Task Force](#)
- ▣ [ITU guide for addressing accessibility in standards](#)
- ▣ [ITU-T analytical report: Informal Survey on human rights integration in ITU-T study groups and TSAG](#)
- ▣ [ITU-T comparative study: Human rights in standards development organizations and other relevant organizations](#)
- ▣ [ISO form on Outcome of procedure on accessibility](#)
- ▣ [Telecommunication Accessibility Checklist](#)
- ▣ [Guidelines for Human Rights Protocol and Architecture Considerations RFC 9620](#)
- ▣ [Report of the OHCHR on “Human rights and technical standard-setting processes for new and emerging digital technologies”](#).
- ▣ [OHCHR study on “Making technical standards work for humanity - New pathways for incorporating international human rights into standards development for digital technologies”](#)

Seminar on Human Rights and ICT Standardisation

14 April 2026
Brussels and Online

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